

UNIFIED TLS CERTIFICATE AUTOMATION USING LET'S ENCRYPT

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

Keywords: TLS, HTTPS, automation, encryption, ACME protocol, HAProxy, DNS API, cybersecurity

Objective: The aim of this report is to implement and evaluate an automated system for managing TLS certificates using the ACME protocol with `acme.sh` client. This solution is expected to simplify certificate issuance and renewal in a scalable and secure way, adaptable to CERN's networking environment.

Scope:

- Research on encryption practices and TLS architecture.
- Investigation of ACME protocol and the `acme.sh` client.
- Development of a basic DNS API for domain validation.
- Integration of automated certificates into a HAProxy-based and Apache-based reverse proxy with Server Name Indication.
- Testing across single-node and proxy-based environments.
- Evaluation of the implementation within CERN's infrastructure constraints.

Deliverables:

- A functional PoC using `acme.sh`.
- Configuration examples for DNS, proxy, and certificates.
- Integration guide tailored for CERN environments.
- Analysis of security benefits and operational limitations.

ABSTRACT

This report presents a study and proof of concept (PoC) for the automation of TLS certificate management using the ACME protocol, within the context of CERN’s infrastructure. It begins with a wide review of key concepts in cybersecurity, particularly encryption, and tackles the growing need for automating certificate issuance and renewal.

The PoC includes the development of a custom DNS API, and automated certificate deployment scenarios, and the integration of HAProxy with Server Name Indication (SNI) for HTTPS termination. Finally, the report evaluates the feasibility of integrating this automated approach within CERN’s existing systems, outlining both the benefits and limitations of using `acme.sh` in production environments.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, a wide range of open-source tools allows anyone with basic knowledge to intercept and inspect data flowing through the Internet. Without proper encryption, sensitive information-such as authentication credentials or personal data-can easily be exposed to malicious actors. This paves the way to serious threats regarding the integrity and confidentiality of web applications.

To protect against such vulnerabilities, it is essential to use SSL/TLS (Secure Sockets Layer / Transport Layer Security) protocols, which encrypt data exchanged between clients and servers. These two protocols are more commonly known to enable https instead of http when surfing a website.

The use of SSL/TLS requires the maintainer of the website to obtain a digital certificate, issued by a trusted Certificate Authority (CA). Currently, at CERN, TLS certificate management for these applications involves several manual steps.

This report introduces a unified solution to automate certificate management across diverse hosting environments at CERN. By leveraging Let's Encrypt -CA used at CERN- over acme.sh -automation tool for Let's Encrypt- , and implementing Server Name Indication (SNI) in the reverse proxy infrastructure, this work enables dynamic and secure handling of certificates on a per-host basis.

This paper details the architecture, implementation, and benefits of this solution, which enhances the security, and scalability of the CERN Application Hosting platform.

2 Background Research

This chapter provides some background research on the project, especially the networking and cyber security background necessary to tackle this issue.

2.1 About cyber-security : Encryption

2.1.1 Why do we have to encrypt the data ?

In today's internet-driven world, most user interactions -such as browsing websites, logging into applications, or accessing online services- involve the exchange of data over public or semi-public networks. These interactions are made possible through the HTTP protocol, which defines how clients and servers communicate over the web. However, while HTTP defines how data is exchanged, it does not address how this data should be secured during transmission. Without **encryption**, this data travels in plain text, making it vulnerable to interception by anyone with access to the network path. And for instance, tools like Wireshark allow even non-experts to capture and analyze network traffic with ease, revealing sensitive information such as login credentials, session cookies, which would be sent somehow in a webpage.

This is where encryption plays a critical role. It ensures that the content of the communication cannot be understood by unauthorized entities, even if the data is intercepted in transit. Without encryption, attackers could impersonate legitimate websites (phishing), steal authentication data, or manipulate web content without the user's knowledge.

Figure 1: Encryption [SSL2BUY]

The importance of encrypting web traffic is now widely recognized, and every web user is able to know if one site is secured thanks to encryption by just looking at the web search bar. If 'HTTPS' is written, it means that the secure (encrypted !) version of HTTP is running, over SSL/TLS.

Figure 2: Example of https with CERN main website

2.1.2 How to encrypt the data ?

Encrypting web traffic is achieved using one of the two following protocols: SSL or TLS, which secure the connection between a client—typically a web browser—and a server. TLS (Transport Layer Security) being the evolved and more secure version of SSL (Secure Sockets Layer). Let's try to understand how these protocols enable encryption.

These protocols relies on two tools : **Cryptographic keys** and **Certificates**.

Cryptographic keys Let's admit that a client wants to send data to a server (for instance a CERN administrator who would want to log to a CERN website by sending its credentials online). The client needs to encrypt the data sent in a way the server -only the server- would be able to decrypt it. This is done by using **cryptographic keys**. Cryptographic keys come in pairs:

- A public key : accessible to anyone, in particular the client ;
- A private key : only known by the server.

Both keys are stored in the server, but only the public key is accessible to anyone, in particular the client. **The client will use this public key to encrypt the data** before sending it. And because the public key was generated by the server, **the server knows how to decrypt the data thanks to his private key**. This is why the private key must be only known by the server, otherwise, the secret is lost !

Figure 3: Encryption between client and server [ClickSSL]

Thanks to encryption, we can make sure that no one is able to understand the encrypted data traveling.

But one breach still remains: how can we be sure that the server we are communicating with is actually the right server, and not an impostor pretending to be it? It would be easy for an impostor to share a public key linked to its own private key, and wait to collect the data it could decrypt.

This is where digital certificates come into play.

Certificates A certificate is an electronic document issued by a trusted Certificate Authority (CA), which check that a given public key truly belongs to a specific domain name (e.g., cern.ch). In other words, it serves to cryptographically bind a public key to a verified identity.

When a client (like a CERN administrator) connects to a website, the server sends its certificate to the client. This certificate contains:

- the server's public key ;
- the domain name it is associated with ;
- the digital signature of the Certificate Authority, which guarantees the certificate's authenticity.

If a server owns a certificate, the client can now send its data, which he will encrypt thanks to a public key provided by the server.

Cryptographic keys + Certificate : TLS protocol Let's now put together Cryptographic keys and Certificates to understand how TLS works. When a user visits a secure website (using HTTPS), their browser and the server perform a TLS handshake. During this handshake, the server presents its certificate, and the browser checks whether it has been signed by a trusted CA. If the certificate is valid and trusted, the browser proceeds to establish an encrypted session : especially sharing the server's public key to the client to encrypt the data.

Figure 4: TLS Handshake [Encryption Consulting]

2.2 About automation : Automation in TLS

2.2.1 What could we automate ?

Each certificate issued by a Certificate Authority (CA) has a validity period, after which it expires and is no longer considered trustworthy.

By default, obtaining and renewing these certificates is a manual process, often requiring system administrators to repeat the validation steps and update certificates before they expire.

When a client wants to **manually** renew a certificate with a Certificate Authority (CA), the process typically involves generating a new Certificate Signing Request (CSR). This CSR contains the client's public key and identifying information (such as the domain name). The client then submits this CSR to the CA, which verifies the information again. If everything is valid, the CA issues a new certificate with a new validity period. The client can then install this renewed certificate on their server to maintain secure connections. This process can be error-prone and difficult to scale in environments hosting many services.

Moreover, the validity period of SSL/TLS certificates will be gradually reduced from the current 398 days to 47 days by 2029. This reduction, decided by the CA/B Forum, aims to strengthen security by limiting the period during which a compromised certificate can be used.

To address this, automated protocols like ACME (Automatic Certificate Management Environment) have emerged. **ACME enables automated certificate issuance.** Automation tools like ACME has become so common that most of the CA have evolved to use them.

2.2.2 ACME protocol

There are nowadays a large range of tools implementing the ACME protocol : the most famous being certbot. The difference between these different tools is how flexible, complicated to set up they are and also on which environment they can be used.

CERN needed a lightweight tool, compatible mostly with Apache and NGINX. Here is how we finally chose the acme.sh client.

The acme.sh client automates the process of obtaining and renewing SSL/TLS certificates by orchestrating secure exchanges between three main components: the client machine, the DNS provider, and the Certificate Authority (CA)-most commonly, Let's Encrypt. Let's understand this point, and the role of each of the three identities.

Use acme.sh The ACME protocol can be used by downloading the acme.sh bash script from GitHub official site : <https://github.com/acmesh-official/acme.sh>. In theory, you have nothing more to do excepted from launching the script to operate the automatic renewal of certificate, using a command such as :

```
acme.sh --issue -d <domain-name-in-need-of-certificate>
```

Note that a lot of additional options can be used while launching the script, as we will mentioned later in this document.

The protocol When such a command is launched by the user, ACME protocol goes on via several steps :

- **Order creation:** The client sends an order request to the CA, specifying the domain name(s) for which a certificate is requested.
- **Challenge retrieval:** The CA responds with one or more domain **validation challenges**, challenge designed to test if the DN is really owned by the pretended machine (e.g., DNS-01, HTTP-01).
In our case, we used a challenge called **DNS-01** which relies on TXT Records. A TXT record is a type of DNS record that stores text-based information about a domain and which is visible to anyone allowed to access the DNS. During the DNS-01 challenge, the CA will send a token (random sequence of numbers) to the server, asking the server to ask its DNS to add a TXT record (based on this token) in : `_acme-challenge.<DN>`.
- **Challenge fulfillment (e.g., DNS-01):**
 - The client creates with the correct token at the domain's DNS zone.
 - The DNS provider publishes the TXT record to make it publicly accessible.
- **Challenge validation:**
 - The client notifies the CA that the challenge is ready.
 - The CA queries the DNS provider to verify the presence and correctness of the TXT record.
- **Certificate issuance:**
 - Once the domain ownership is validated, the client sends a Certificate Signing Request (CSR) to the CA.
 - The CA signs and issues the certificate.
- **Certificate installation:** The client installs the new certificate on its server to enable secure HTTPS communication.

Why DNS-01 Challenge ? As we said, to prove ownership of these domain(s), `acme.sh` supports several challenge types, the most common being HTTP-01 and DNS-01. The HTTP-01 challenge requires serving a specific token via a publicly accessible web server, while the DNS-01 challenge involves creating a special TXT record in the DNS zone of the domain. In our case, the DNS-01 challenge was chosen, as many of the services involved were not accessible from outside CERN's internal network, making HTTP-based validation infeasible.

The next page contains a visual description of the ACME protocol using `acme.sh`. You can also find some more information about the `acme` command in the Appendix. Make sure to look at this diagram as we will update it through the paragraphs.

Figure 5: ACME protocol

3 The Proof Of Concept

3.1 Coding a DNS API

3.1.1 Why ?

Unlike many organizations who rely on public DNS providers offering public and standardized APIs, CERN does not have a single, unified external DNS provider with a comprehensive API suited for this automation.

Because of this limitation, it is not possible to directly leverage common DNS automation tools or scripts designed for popular providers. Hence the need to develop a custom DNS API that can interface with its internal DNS infrastructure. This API will enable automated creation, updating, and deletion of DNS TXT records required by protocols like ACME for domain validation.

To reach this API, we must launch the `acme.sh` script with the following option :

```
--dns <name-of-the-API-script>
```

Note that the script must be stored in a specific folder, in the `acme` repo you cloned in your machine : **`acme.sh/dnsapi/`**

So let's update the visual explanation of ACME protocol to show how it works with a customized DNS API. As you can see, the API is now on the same machine than `acme.sh` script because the script needs to call the API, which is stored in the specific folder we mentioned.

- (1) `acme.sh --issue --dns dns_myapi -d <DN> --challenge --debug --server letsencrypt`
- (2) `key_authorization = token + '.' + base64url(thumbprint(account_key))`
`txt record = base64url(SHA256(key_authorization))`

Figure 6: ACME protocol with custumed API

3.1.2 How ?

Let's now give a look on the API : what are the main functions of it ?

```
#!/usr/bin/env bash

# This script automates DNS-01 challenge using nsupdate and Let's Encrypt.

##### Public functions #####

# export MYAPI="1" to indicate compatibility
MYAPI="1"
_debug() {
    echo "[DEBUG] $@" >&2
}

_err() {
    echo "[ERROR] $@" >&2
}

# Called by acme.sh to add the TXT record
dns_myapi_add() {
    fulldomain="$1"
    txtvalue="$2"

    _debug "Adding TXT record for domain: $fulldomain"
    _debug "TXT value: $txtvalue"

    # Detect zone root
    _debug "First detect the root zone"
    if ! _get_root "$fulldomain"; then
        _err "Cannot determine root zone for $fulldomain"
        return 1
    fi

    subdomain="_acme-challenge"

    _debug "Zone: $ZONE"
    _debug "Subdomain for update: $subdomain"

    (
        echo "server <IP-of-server>"
        echo "zone $ZONE"
        echo update add ${subdomain}.${ZONE} 60 IN TXT "$txtvalue"
        echo "send"
        echo "quit"
    ) | /usr/bin/nsupdate -y "$MYAPI_Username:$MYAPI_Password"
```



```

    _debug "nsupdate command sent"

    return 0
}

# Called by acme.sh to remove the TXT record
dns_myapi_rm() {
    fulldomain="$1"
    txtvalue="$2"

    _debug "Removing TXT record for domain: $fulldomain"
    _debug "TXT value: $txtvalue"

    if ! _get_root "$fulldomain"; then
        _err "Cannot determine root zone for $fulldomain"
        return 1
    fi

    subdomain="_acme-challenge"

    (
        echo "server <IP-of-server>"
        echo "zone $ZONE"
        echo update delete ${subdomain}.${ZONE} 60 IN TXT "$txtvalue"
        echo "send"
        echo "quit"
    ) | /usr/bin/nsupdate -y "$MYAPI_Username:$MYAPI_Password"

    return 0
}

# txt challenge made for the subdomain _acme-challenge.db-lb-k8s-321.cern.ch,
# for the root domain db-lb-k8s-321.cern.ch
_get_root() {
    domain=$1
    while true; do
        if host -t ns "$domain" >/dev/null 2>&1; then
            ZONE=$domain
            return 0
        fi
        domain="${domain#*.*}"
        if [[ -z "$domain" ]]; then
            return 1
        fi
    done
}

```



```

fi

    _debug "Determined zone: $ZONE"

done
}

#####
# LAUNCH WITH acme.sh --issue --dns dns_myapi -d <CNAME-of-domain>
# --challenge-alias <real-DN> --debug --server letsencrypt

#ex : acme.sh --issue --dns dns_myapi -d amelie-letsencrypt-test.cern.ch
# --challenge-alias db-lb-k8s-321.cern.ch --debug --server letsencrypt

#def : fulldomain="_acme-challenge.db-lb-k8s-321.cern.ch",
# ZONE=db-lb-k8s-321.cern.ch, subdomain="_acme-challenge"

#The file must be placed in acme.sh/ folder, or in acme.sh/dnsapi/ subfolder

```

The API got three functions :

- **dns_myapi_add()** : function to add a TXT record on the DNS, based on nsupdate command.
- **dns_myapi_rm()** : function to remove a TXT record on the DNS, based on nsupdate command.
- **_get_root()** : function called before using nsupdate in dns_myapi_add() and dns_myapi_rm(), to identify the zone and the root of the domain from the input acme.sh command.

What is important to note in this script is that the TXT record is not added to the DN directly during the DNS-01 challenge, but it is added to "_acme-challenge.<DN>" Let's Encrypt will indeed perform the verification on that specific label, dedicated to the DNS-01 challenge.

3.2 POC on a single DN, without proxy

It is now time to put in a nutshell this topic in a proof of concept.

First issuing a certificate for a single DN, then for three DN, all managed by a Proxy+SNI.

Automatizing on a cern.ch subdomain The proof of concept for a single VM is simple :

- A Linux (Ubuntu) VM on which is downloaded the acme.sh script ;
- A DN linked with the VM IP : "amelie-letsencrypt-test.cern.ch"

As we said, these two things set up, one could just launch the acme command to get a certificate. But at CERN, things are different.

Figure 8: CNAME issue with ACME

As depicted in this graph the first and clearest solution is to add an additionnal CNAME `_acme-challenge.<CNAME-of-domain> => _acme-challenge.<real-DN>`

Another solution, could also obviously be to get rid of CNAME.

These are compromises to discuss with stakeholders in the CERN networking infrastructure. For experiment purpose, we tried to add a CNAME between the two challenge subdomains. It worked and we managed to get a certificate for the CNAME.

Note that the final launching command is :

```
acme.sh --issue --dns dns_myapi -d <CNAME-of-domain> --challenge-alias <real-DN> --debug --server letsencrypt
```



```

FC:6D:35:BF:06:B0:8D:D9:E0:A2:51:68:97:7E:42:57:
93:01:35:1C:02:20:16:5E:5D:7D:F8:63:33:57:15:AE:
8A:97:45:3D:6A:E9:0D:77:07:DC:F9:3F:AF:8C:C5:19:
0F:3D:3D:48:ED:97
Signed Certificate Timestamp:
Version      : v1(0)
Log ID       : DD:DC:CA:34:95:D7:E1:16:05:E7:95:32:FA:C7:9F:F8:
              3D:1C:50:DF:D8:00:3A:14:12:76:0A:2C:AC:8B:C8:2A
Timestamp    : Jul 22 09:38:50.312 2025 GMT
Extensions   : none
Signature    : ecdsa-with-SHA256
              30:44:02:20:44:D8:0B:D9:3F:80:88:8F:50:69:77:81:
              41:8C:43:58:8C:AB:83:EA:60:B5:A1:DC:9D:26:AB:E0:
              E5:EB:03:FA:02:20:41:89:A7:95:B4:91:8D:B6:FA:F8:
              7A:BB:2C:72:B1:F6:0D:52:A8:4B:EB:C9:AC:25:34:4A:
              F9:6A:9A:2A:AE:E8
Signature Algorithm: ecdsa-with-SHA384
              30:64:02:30:37:a6:22:f9:86:84:81:04:54:94:af:d9:d9:c6:
              83:3a:78:60:98:4b:01:37:f4:cb:27:7d:2d:c3:5e:51:dc:00:
              84:8c:4e:56:4c:8b:19:5c:8d:78:3a:1e:93:42:0c:e7:02:30:
              7d:9c:3b:6c:5d:fa:3a:32:fe:b7:9c:d7:40:45:97:b8:90:25:
              92:a3:f2:c6:0b:45:2c:3a:7f:3c:8e:42:f9:32:4e:b5:b2:87:
              71:11:96:f2:1b:98:1c:29:7c:43:22:aa
[Tue Jul 22 09:38:51 UTC 2025] Cert success.
-----BEGIN CERTIFICATE-----
MIIDqTCCAzCgAwIBAgISBm6XGqTZvIR+Kw4oqzCnkST8MAoGCCqGSM49BAMDMDIx
CzAJBgNVBAYTA1VTRyYwFAyDVoQKQWwMTAaMBgNVBAWMT2Ft
NTAeFwYwNTA3MjIwODQwMTAaFwYwNTA3MjIwODQwMTAaMBgNVBAWMT2Ft
ZWxpZS1sZXRzZW5jcmlwdC10ZXN0LmNlcm4uY2gwWTATBgqhkhj0PQIBBgqhkhj0
PQMBBwNCAAQ6dYDhPPDYggjwGbnx9FvUCHfnI9g8zCKZ/yN1B12ndwSHI.JuhB2f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-----END CERTIFICATE-----
[Tue Jul 22 09:38:51 UTC 2025] Your cert is in: /home/ubuntu/.acme.sh/amelie-letsencrypt-test.cern.ch_ecc/amelie-letsencrypt-test.cern.ch.cer
[Tue Jul 22 09:38:51 UTC 2025] Your cert key is in: /home/ubuntu/.acme.sh/amelie-letsencrypt-test.cern.ch_ecc/amelie-letsencrypt-test.cern.ch.key
[Tue Jul 22 09:38:51 UTC 2025] The intermediate CA cert is in: /home/ubuntu/.acme.sh/amelie-letsencrypt-test.cern.ch_ecc/ca.cer
[Tue Jul 22 09:38:51 UTC 2025] And the full-chain cert is in: /home/ubuntu/.acme.sh/amelie-letsencrypt-test.cern.ch_ecc/fullchain.cer
[Tue Jul 22 09:38:51 UTC 2025] _on_issue_success

```

Figure 9: Cert success

The following diagram is the updated one with the additional CNAME
 _acme-challenge.<CNAME-of-domain> => _acme-challenge.<real-DN> :

(1) `acme.sh --issue --dns dns_myapi -d <CNAME-of-domain> --challenge-alias <real-DN> --challenge --debug --server letsencrypt`

(2) `key_authorization = token + ' ' + base64url(thumbprint(account_key))`
`txt record = base64url(SHA256(key_authorization))`

Figure 10: Successful ACME protocol with CNAME

3.3 POC three DN's with proxy+SNI

Let's now understand how certificate management can get along with Proxy and SNI. Let's first define what these two concepts are:

- **Proxy:** A proxy is an intermediary server that sits between a client and a destination server. It forwards client requests to the destination server and can modify, inspect, or filter traffic if needed.
- **SNI (Server Name Indication):** SNI is an extension to the TLS protocol that allows a client to indicate the hostname to which it is trying to connect at the start of the TLS handshake. This is used in environments where multiple domains are hosted on the same IP address, allowing the server (or proxy) to present the correct certificate for the requested hostname.

Thus, by combining the use of a proxy with proper SNI support, one can ensure both secure and accurate TLS termination. The proxy acts as a centralized control point : functioning not only as a basic firewall by filtering traffic (proxy main function), but also as a load balancer by routing requests to the appropriate backend, based on the requested hostname (SNI main function).

3.3.1 Proxy modes

You can configure your proxy in two different ways:

- **TLS Passthrough:** In this mode, the proxy does not decrypt the traffic. It simply forwards the encrypted TLS packets to the backend server. The TLS handshake and certificate exchange occur directly between the client and the backend server. Since the proxy does not see the decrypted content, it doesn't need access to the TLS certificates.
- **TLS Termination:** In this mode, the proxy decrypts the incoming TLS connection, acting as the endpoint of the TLS handshake. It requires a valid certificate for the requested domain, which it selects using the SNI provided by the client. After decryption, the proxy can inspect, log, or modify traffic, and may re-encrypt it to the backend server. This mode enables better routing and security policies, but also places the responsibility of certificate management on the proxy.

The following diagram shows the difference between these two modes.

Figure 11: TLS Passthrough VS TLS terminaison

We chose to implement **TLS termination** at the proxy level primarily for security reasons. By terminating TLS on the proxy, we ensure that all incoming traffic is decrypted and inspected before reaching the back-end servers. It also prevents external clients from establishing direct connections to backend services, isolating the internal infrastructure.

3.3.2 Proxy configuration with SNI

Here is the code of the proxy configuration used during our proof of concept, to serve 3DNs, all three hosted on the same Virtual Machine, as depicted on the previous diagram : We will explain straight after the logic of such a configuration.

Stored in `/usr/local/etc/haproxy/haproxy.conf`:

```
global
  log          127.0.0.1 local2
  chroot      /var/lib/haproxy
  pidfile     /var/run/haproxy.pid
  maxconn     4000
  user        haproxy
```



```

group      haproxy
daemon
stats socket /var/lib/haproxy/stats

defaults
  mode                http
  log                 global
  option              httplog
  timeout connect     10s
  timeout client      1m
  timeout server      1m
  maxconn             3000

#-----
# FRONTEND : TLS termination (avec SNI, plusieurs certs)
#-----
frontend https_front
  bind *:443 ssl crt /etc/ssl/haproxy/ # here are all the .pem
  mode http
  option forwardfor
  http-request set-header X-Forwarded-Proto https

  use_backend backend_321_http if { ssl_fc_sni -i db-lb-k8s-321.cern.ch }
  use_backend backend_322_http if { ssl_fc_sni -i db-lb-k8s-322.cern.ch }
  use_backend backend_326_http if { ssl_fc_sni -i db-lb-k8s-326.cern.ch }

#-----
# BACKENDS HTTP
#-----
backend backend_321_http
  mode http
  server db1 <IP>:8080 check

backend backend_322_http
  mode http
  server db2 <IP>:8181 check

backend backend_326_http
  mode http
  server db3 <IP>:8282 check

#certif stored at /etc/ssl/acme/db-lb-k8s-321.cern.ch/fullchain.pem
#/etc/ssl/acme/db-lb-k8s-321.cern.ch/privkey.pem

```

Here are the two most important things about the code :

- We connected three backend servers using SNI (Server Name Indication). HAProxy inspects the hostname requested in the TLS handshake and chooses the appropriate backend based on that value.

- The certificates are read by the proxy from the following path: `/etc/ssl/haproxy/`. Each certificate must be in `.pem` format, containing both the private key and fullchain certificate (we will specify in next paragraph what it is). They must be placed here manually or automatically (e.g., by configuring Let’s Encrypt or another ACME client to store or symlink the certs there).

The following diagram sum up the mechanics :

Figure 12: HAproxy configuration mechanics

3.3.3 Backend servers

In order to assign each DN a service that could listen on the port, we decided to setup three simple python server on port 80,81 and 82.

Here is the code of one of the server :

```

from http.server import HTTPServer, SimpleHTTPRequestHandler
PORT = 8080
server_address = ('', PORT)
httpd = HTTPServer(server_address, SimpleHTTPRequestHandler)
print("Port {}".format(PORT)) httpd.serve_forever()
    
```

3.3.4 Final test

Let’s put in a nutshell all the previous subjects we tackled in the following experiment :

1. In the VM are the acme.sh and the three Python servers, each related to a DN ;
2. Launch acme.sh to generate a certificate for each one of the three DNS, acme.sh will provide three files per DN :
 - the private key of the DN, to decrypt the incoming data ;

- the certificate for the DN ;
 - A `fullchain.pem` file containing:
 - The domain certificate;
 - The chain of intermediate certificates;
 - (Optionally) the root certificate, but this is often omitted (HTTPS clients generally don't require it).
3. Concatenate for each DN the private key + `fullchain.pem` and put it in the right file in the HAproxy (`/etc/ssl/haproxy/`) ;
 4. Restart the `haproxy.service` so that it updates the certificates ;
 5. Try to get the secured webpage on a browser.

These steps were successful using the previous configurations, we could check it by using `openssl` command, or by getting a secured link from one browser, as depicted on the following screenshots.


```

$ openssl s_client -connect db-lb-k8s-322.cern.ch:443 --showcerts
Connecting to ██████████
CONNECTED(00000003)
depth=2 C=US, O=Internet Security Research Group, CN=ISRG Root X1
verify return:1
depth=1 C=US, O=Let's Encrypt, CN=E6
verify return:1
depth=0 CN=db-lb-k8s-322.cern.ch
verify return:1
---
Certificate chain
 0 s:CN=db-lb-k8s-322.cern.ch
  i:C=US, O=Let's Encrypt, CN=E6
  a:PKEY: id-ecPublicKey, 256 (bit); sigalg: ecdsa-with-SHA384
  v:NotBefore: Jul 25 11:31:37 2025 GMT; NotAfter: Oct 23 11:31:36 2025 GMT
-----BEGIN CERTIFICATE-----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-----END CERTIFICATE-----
 1 s:C=US, O=Let's Encrypt, CN=E6
  i:C=US, O=Internet Security Research Group, CN=ISRG Root X1
  a:PKEY: id-ecPublicKey, 384 (bit); sigalg: RSA-SHA256
  v:NotBefore: Mar 13 00:00:00 2024 GMT; NotAfter: Mar 12 23:59:59 2027 GMT
-----BEGIN CERTIFICATE-----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```

Figure 13: Certificate for db-lb-k8s-322.cern.ch, openssl

Figure 14: Secured connection for db-lb-k8s-322.cern.ch from browser

Figure 15: Certificate for db-lb-k8s-322.cern.ch from the browser

4 Integration on CERN infrastructure

What with a Apache and Kubernetes environnement ?

4.1 Apache Proxy

Let's now replace our HAproxy by an Apache Proxy (under AlmaLinux).

For this POC, we won't use two Virtual Machines like we did previously. No python server neither. We will simply edit 3 simple HTML pages, hosted on the proxy and routed by the SNI.

This part of the report only aims to provide a functional configuration file for this type of proxy.

4.1.1 Configuration

Here is the configuration of the Apache Proxy, stored in `/etc/httpd/conf.d/db-lb-k8s.conf` :

```
<VirtualHost *:443>
  ServerName db-lb-k8s-321.cern.ch

  SSLEngine on
  SSLCertificateFile /etc/ssl/acme/db-lb-k8s-321/fullchain.pem
  SSLCertificateKeyFile /etc/ssl/acme/db-lb-k8s-321/privkey.pem
  SSLStrictSNIVHostCheck on

  DocumentRoot /var/www/db-lb-k8s-321

  RequestHeader set X-Forwarded-Proto "https"

  ErrorLog /var/log/httpd/db-lb-k8s-321_error.log
  CustomLog /var/log/httpd/db-lb-k8s-321_access.log combined
</VirtualHost>

<VirtualHost *:443>
  ServerName db-lb-k8s-322.cern.ch

  SSLEngine on
  SSLCertificateFile /etc/ssl/acme/db-lb-k8s-322/fullchain.pem
  SSLCertificateKeyFile /etc/ssl/acme/db-lb-k8s-322/privkey.pem
  SSLStrictSNIVHostCheck on

  DocumentRoot /var/www/db-lb-k8s-322

  RequestHeader set X-Forwarded-Proto "https"

  ErrorLog /var/log/httpd/db-lb-k8s-322_error.log
  CustomLog /var/log/httpd/db-lb-k8s-322_access.log combined
</VirtualHost>
```



```
<VirtualHost *:443>
  ServerName db-lb-k8s-326.cern.ch

  SSLEngine on
  SSLCertificateFile /etc/ssl/acme/db-lb-k8s-326/fullchain.pem
  SSLCertificateKeyFile /etc/ssl/acme/db-lb-k8s-326/privkey.pem
  SSLStrictSNIVHostCheck on

  DocumentRoot /var/www/db-lb-k8s-326

  RequestHeader set X-Forwarded-Proto "https"

  ErrorLog /var/log/httpd/db-lb-k8s-326_error.log
  CustomLog /var/log/httpd/db-lb-k8s-326_access.log combined
</VirtualHost>
```

4.1.2 HTML pages

Here are the HTML page configuration, stored in `/var/www/db-lb-k8s-32x` (this is the exemple for `db-lb-k8s-321`) :

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="fr">
<head>
  <meta charset="UTF-8">
  <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
  <title>Server db-lb-k8s-321 Webpage</title>
</head>
<body>
  <h1>Welcome on db-lb-k8s-321.cern.ch</h1>
</body>
</html>
```

4.1.3 Some useful CLI command I had to use.

- **Check Apache version:** Ensure your Apache (httpd) version supports SNI.

```
httpd -v
```

- **Check required modules:** Ensure the necessary Apache modules (like SSL) are loaded.

```
httpd -M | grep ssl
```


- **Enable mod_ssl:** Install and ensure 'mod_ssl' is enabled (via package).

```
sudo dnf install mod_ssl
```

- **Enable mod_proxy:** To enable reverse proxy functionality.

```
sudo dnf install httpd
# proxy modules are usually built-in, but verify with:
httpd -M | grep proxy
```

- **Check SSL configuration files:** Ensure certificates and keys are configured in your SSL virtual host files (usually in '/etc/httpd/conf.d/ssl.conf' or custom vhosts).

```
sudo apachectl configtest
```

- **Restart Apache after any changes:** Restart Apache to apply configuration changes.

```
sudo systemctl restart httpd
```

- **Check proxy HTTPS connectivity:** Use 'curl' to test your reverse proxy setup.

```
curl -v https://your-domain.com
```

- **Check Apache logs:** View error logs for troubleshooting.

```
tail -f /var/log/httpd/error_log
```

- **Test with SNI:** Test SSL connectivity and verify the correct certificate is served.

```
openssl s_client -connect your-domain.com:443 -servername your-domain.com
```

- **Active Vhosts:** List all virtual hosts and their configuration.

```
apachectl -S
```

- **Confirm Apache is listening on expected ports:**

```
sudo netstat -tulnp | grep httpd
```


4.2 Kubernetes environment

4.2.1 Roadmap

The goal is to study the certificate management for the following kubernetes cluster :

Figure 16: Kubernetes cluster

You can see that the decryption is made at the step of the ingress controller and not at the step of the Loadbalancer. It enables more control on the data and a better secret.

In order to work in TLS terminaison that way, the goal is to create some kubernetes secrets, defined in each ingress, and which contains the fullchain certificate+decryption key. Here are some useful information for the setup :

- Create ingress on node worker :


```
kubectl apply -f https://raw.githubusercontent.com/kubernetes/ingress-nginx/controller-v1.10.1/deploy/static/provider/cloud/deploy.yaml
```

- Set up an external NGINX loadbalancer, which only forward all the encrypted incoming data to the ingress controller (we will provide the configuration later)
- Make sure that you have stored the fullchain and the key of each DN somewhere in the cluster. You can then create secret associated with the certificates with the following commands :

```
kubectl create secret tls <name-of-the-secret>
-cert=<path-to-fullchain>
-key=<path-to-key>
-n default
```

- Each ingress must be in the same namespace than the TLS secret !!
- If one secret is changed, the ingress controller needs to be reloaded, and it can take time before everything works again : **kubectl rollout restart deployment ingress-nginx-controller -n ingress-nginx**

Official documentation : <https://kubernetes.io/docs/tasks/tls/managing-tls-in-a-cluster/>

4.2.2 Configuration files

Here are the configurations of several components of the cluster :

Ingress Controller

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  annotations:
    kubectl.kubernetes.io/last-applied-configuration: |
      {"apiVersion":"v1","kind":"Service","metadata":{"annotations":{},"labels":{"app.ku
creationTimestamp: "2025-08-07T07:22:43Z"
labels:
  app.kubernetes.io/component: controller
  app.kubernetes.io/instance: ingress-nginx
  app.kubernetes.io/name: ingress-nginx
  app.kubernetes.io/part-of: ingress-nginx
  app.kubernetes.io/version: 1.10.1
name: ingress-nginx-controller
namespace: ingress-nginx
resourceVersion: "508909"
uid: c8f2731d-e2a1-48c1-a9ca-075eed981a12
spec:
  clusterIP: 10.254.52.82
  clusterIPs:
  - 10.254.52.82
  externalTrafficPolicy: Cluster
  internalTrafficPolicy: Cluster
```



```

ipFamilies:
- IPv4
ipFamilyPolicy: SingleStack
ports:
- name: http
  nodePort: 30080
  port: 80
  protocol: TCP
  targetPort: http
- name: https
  nodePort: 30443
  port: 443
  protocol: TCP
  targetPort: https
selector:
  app.kubernetes.io/component: controller
  app.kubernetes.io/instance: ingress-nginx
  app.kubernetes.io/name: ingress-nginx
sessionAffinity: None
type: NodePort
status:
  loadBalancer: {}

```

Ingress ressource, 1 conf file for all three ingresses

```

# ingress.yaml
apiVersion: networking.k8s.io/v1
kind: Ingress
metadata:
  name: sites-ingress
  namespace: default
  annotations:
    nginx.ingress.kubernetes.io/ssl-redirect: "true"

spec:
  ingressClassName: nginx
  tls:
  - hosts:
    - db-lb-k8s-321.cern.ch
      secretName: tls-321
  - hosts:
    - db-lb-k8s-322.cern.ch
      secretName: tls-322
  - hosts:
    - db-lb-k8s-326.cern.ch
      secretName: tls-326

  rules:

```



```

- host: db-lb-k8s-321.cern.ch
  http:
    paths:
      - path: /
        pathType: Prefix
        backend:
          service:
            name: db-lb-k8s-321-cern-ch
            port:
              number: 80
- host: db-lb-k8s-322.cern.ch
  http:
    paths:
      - path: /
        pathType: Prefix
        backend:
          service:
            name: db-lb-k8s-322-cern-ch
            port:
              number: 80
- host: db-lb-k8s-326.cern.ch
  http:
    paths:
      - path: /
        pathType: Prefix
        backend:
          service:
            name: db-lb-k8s-326-cern-ch
            port:
              number: 80

```

Pod configs

```

apiVersion: v1
kind: Pod
metadata:
  name: db-lb-k8s-321-cern-ch
  labels:
    app: db-lb-k8s-321-cern-ch
spec:
  containers:
    - name: nginx
      image: nginx
      volumeMounts:
        - name: html
          mountPath: /usr/share/nginx/html
  volumes:
    - name: html
      configMap:

```



```
    name: db-lb-k8s-321-cern-ch-html
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: ConfigMap
metadata:
  name: db-lb-k8s-321-cern-ch-html
data:
  index.html: |
    <html><body><h1>Welcome on db-lb-k8s-321</h1></body></html>
---
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: db-lb-k8s-321-cern-ch
spec:
  selector:
    app: db-lb-k8s-321-cern-ch
  ports:
    - port: 80
      targetPort: 80
```

LoadBalancer config files

```
load_module /usr/lib64/nginx/modules/nginx_stream_module.so;
```

```
events {
    worker_connections 1024;
}

stream {
    upstream ingress_https {
        server <IP>:30443;
    }

    server {
        listen 443;
        proxy_pass ingress_https;
    }
}
```


4.2.3 Results

Welcome on db-lb-k8s-321

Figure 17: Secured connexion from the kubernetes cluster.

Figure 18: GET https logs for 321

Figure 19: Kubernetes secrets

4.2.4 Debug commands I used

- Check that the good certificate is used by the DN : `curl -vk https://db-lb-k8s-321.cern.ch`]
- Check that secrets are read : `kubectl logs ingress-nginx-controller-6bb485db4b-95dpb -n ingress-nginx | grep tls-`

Official documentation : <https://kubernetes.io/docs/tasks/tls/managing-tls-in-a-cluster/>

5 Conclusion

5.1 Pros acme.sh

Here is a list of advantages of using acme.sh script, which I could experienced during this project :

- **No dependencies** : Unlike other ACME clients, acme.sh is written in shell script, meaning there is no need to install other heavy dependencies. This makes it particularly convenient for environments where lightweight tooling is preferred.
- **Flexible configuration options**: acme.sh supports multiple certificate types, including wildcards and multi-domain certificates, and allows custom configurations through a simple script interface. We have seen it with the use of our custom API along this project.
- **Support for HTTP and TLS-ALPN Challenges**: In addition to DNS challenges, acme.sh also supports HTTP-01 and TLS-ALPN-01 challenges, providing more flexibility for certificate validation depending on the environment or specific use case. We did not try to configure other type of challenge during this project, but one could find many online ressources explaining how to implement it.
- **Open-Source**: acme.sh is an open-source project, meaning that users can contribute to its development or report bugs, and they benefit from regular updates and improvements from the community.

5.2 Limits of acme.sh

We could not witness many bugs on the script, and this section could deserve an entire audit. But still, two issues caught our attention :

5.2.1 TXT record not empty on challenge subdomain

The first point I struggled with is the following one :

ACME protocol used with dns-01 is based on adding TXT records, as we have seen it. During test sessions, many TXT records were added and removed. What we observed is that if the TXT record field is not blank before launching the acme.sh script, the TXT record will never be registered in the DNS, and the command will end up in an endless loop stuck at the public DNS verification state.

This issue is tricky because it was never explained in the logs of the command, and can be even more complicated to spot because of the DNS time propagation.

Conclusion : Always launch acme.sh script with a wiped TXT record zone.

5.2.2 Openssl showcert with SNI disabled.

The issue By using `-noservername` option with the openssl command, meaning asking to see a certificate while disabling the SNI, we could still achieve to get one certificate, as shown in the following screenshot :


```

|$ openssl s_client -connect db-lb-k8s-322.cern.ch:443 -showcerts -noservername
Connecting to [REDACTED]
CONNECTED(00000003)
depth=2 C=US, O=Internet Security Research Group, CN=ISRG Root X1
verify return:1
depth=1 C=US, O=Let's Encrypt, CN=E6
verify return:1
depth=0 CN=amelie-letsencrypt-test.cern.ch
verify return:1
---
Certificate chain
 0 s:CN=amelie-letsencrypt-test.cern.ch
  i:C=US, O=Let's Encrypt, CN=E6
  a:PKEY: id-ecPublicKey, 256 (bit); sigalg: ecdsa-with-SHA384
  v:NotBefore: Jul 21 06:44:14 2025 GMT; NotAfter: Oct 19 06:44:13 2025 GMT
-----BEGIN CERTIFICATE-----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-----END CERTIFICATE-----
 1 s:C=US, O=Let's Encrypt, CN=E6
  i:C=US, O=Internet Security Research Group, CN=ISRG Root X1
  a:PKEY: id-ecPublicKey, 384 (bit); sigalg: RSA-SHA256
  v:NotBefore: Mar 13 00:00:00 2024 GMT; NotAfter: Mar 12 23:59:59 2027 GMT
-----BEGIN CERTIFICATE-----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```

Figure 20: Showcert, SNI disabled.

This issue could be observed for both proxy types (HAproxy and Apache).

What is happening By deactivating the SNI, we are querying the proxy without mentioning which DN we want to query. In that context, the Proxy respond with a default certificate : the first one in alphabetical order OR first one in the config file (depending on the Linux

distribution you use).

Why is it an issue The core issue stems from the reliance on Server Name Indication (SNI) to serve the correct SSL/TLS certificate in environments hosting multiple domains on the same IP address. When SNI is disabled or unsupported—as may be the case with some legacy systems, IoT devices, or outdated clients—the server defaults to returning a fallback certificate, which may not match the requested domain. This can result in trust errors, failed connections, or unintended exposure of the default certificate.

Solution

- Configure a default backend named 000-default.conf which will be served by default. The HTML file linked with this backend could provide an explanation page pleasing the client to use a device supporting SNI.
- Use wildcard certificates : or at least configure your proxy to serve a wildcard certificate in case the client does not support SNI. This can be done by using a wildcard certificate on the first subdomain (the one that would be queried if SNI is down).

NB : We also tried to display a 403 error by adding the following line to the Apache configuration file (apache2.conf, or httpd.conf): `SSLStrictSNIVHostCheck on`. But this can't work as our proxy works in TLS termination : SNI required message defined in the fallback `VirtualHost` is part of the HTTP layer, but in this case the TLS handshake either fails or does not proceed beyond the initial negotiation due to the missing SNI. In our context — where Apache acts as a TLS termination proxy and forwards decrypted traffic to backends over plain HTTP — this means that the 403 error page can only be served after successful decryption of the TLS session. Since we are trying to return an HTTP error before TLS decryption is even possible, it will never be delivered to the client.

Default backend configuration About the default configuration page :

- it is using a self-signed certificate for our POC, but could use a real certificate. Ours was generated via the following command :

```
openssl req -x509 -nodes -days 365 -newkey rsa:2048
-keyout /etc/pki/tls/private/fallback.key
-out /etc/pki/tls/certs/fallback.crt
-subj "/CN=default-fallback".
```
- it provides a fallback when the client does not send SNI, create a dedicated `VirtualHost` listening on port 443 with SSL enabled (`SSLEngine on`),
- one can check that the expected error page is correctly served with :

```
printf "GET / HTTP/1.1\r\nHost: db-lb-k8s-321.cern.ch\r\nConnection: close\r\n\r\n"
| openssl s_client -connect db-lb-k8s-321.cern.ch:443 -noservername -quiet
```

NB : The same issue can be solved with the same steps for an HAproxy, as mentioned here : <https://www.haproxy.com/blog/enhanced-ssl-load-balancing-with-server-name-indication-sni>

Finally, here is the html code of the default backend server :


```
frontend https-in
    bind *:443 ssl crt /etc/haproxy/certs/ alpn h2,http/1.1
    mode http

    acl no_sni req_ssl_sni -m len 0
    http-request deny deny_status 403 if no_sni

    default_backend my_backend
```

5.3 What is next ?

5.3.1 More automation

As we said, there is still one manual step remaining: in this POC, we had to concatenate for each DN the private key + fullchain.pem and put it in the right file in haproxy. This step can be automated natively by Let's Encrypt, using the `- reloadcmd` option.

This option will launch every command you decide to write. For instance, we could imagine doing this :

```
--reloadcmd "scp /etc/ssl/acme/<DN>/* user@haproxy-vm:/etc/haproxy/ \\  
&& systemctl reload haproxy"
```

This stands as a simple example, and it takes for granted that no step of authentication is required between the VM (hosting certificates and acme script) and the proxy.

5.3.2 About Wildcard certificates

Let's shed a light on wildcard certificates, since they were part of our research. The goal is to understand what they are and why we did not use it.

Definition A wildcard certificate is a type of public key certificate (like SSL/TLS) that secures a primary domain and all its first-level subdomains. Instead of needing a separate certificate for each subdomain, a single wildcard certificate can be used, saving time and cost, especially for businesses with multiple subdomains.

The certificate is identified by an asterisk (*) in the domain name, such as *.example.com.

Case of use At first sight, this kind of certificate seems really convenient. Moreover, it could solve our issue about CNAME (see 3.2). But in reality, this kind of certificate can raise many security issues such as :

- Private key compromission : the private key associated with the wildcard certificate is shared across all secured subdomains. This means if the private key is compromised, all those subdomains are vulnerable.
- Limited control over individual subdomains: since wildcard certificates apply to all subdomains under a primary domain, you lose the ability to manage each subdomain individually. For example, if one subdomain is compromised or needs a change in security settings (e.g., key rotation), you would have to update the certificate for all other subdomains too, which can be problematic.

- Risk of certificate mismanagement: since wildcard certificates cover many subdomains, it becomes essential to carefully manage and rotate them. If a wildcard certificate is not properly managed, such as neglecting to renew or revoke it when needed, it could lead to widespread security vulnerabilities across all the subdomains.

6 Appendix

6.1 Other works

6.1.1 Final acme.sh command used for the POC

Let's have a look on the ACME command. Here it is :

```
acme.sh --issue --dns dns_myapi -d <CNAME-of-domain>
--challenge-alias <real-DN> --debug --server letsencrypt
```

is used to request an SSL/TLS certificate from Let's Encrypt using the `acme.sh` client with specific options tailored to automate and debug the process.

- `--issue` tells the client to start the certificate issuance process.
- `--dns dns_myapi` specifies the DNS validation method. When the server rely on a public provider, you have to commit this option, because the prvider has its own API. Otherwise, `dns_myapi` refers to a custom DNS API script or configuration that enables `acme.sh` to interact with the DNS to create the necessary TXT records for domain validation.
- `-d <CNAME-of-domain>` indicates the domain name for which the certificate is requested.
- `--challenge-alias <real-DN>` indicates on which DN should be operated the DNS01 challenge.
- `--debug` activates verbose logging to provide detailed information during the process, which is useful for troubleshooting and ensuring that each step completes correctly.
- `--server letsencrypt` explicitly specifies that the certificate should be requested from the Let's Encrypt CA (as opposed to another ACME-compatible CA). If you don't put it, the CA used will be ZeroSSL by default.
- Use `--test` to run tests, otherwise, there is a maximum number of certificate generation attempts !

Together, these options enable automated, DNS-based domain validation and certificate issuance for a customed API, with detailed feedback during execution and a defined certificate authority.

6.1.2 Updating the change-dns.py code

One side-quest of this project was also to update a script used in my team to change DNS IP. I could update it to add and remove some TXT records on a DN.

You can find the updated script there : https://gitlab.cern.ch/jeedy/load-balancer/letsencrypt/-/blob/master/change_dns_updated_txtrecords.py?ref_type=heads

I did not add any function compared to the original script, but modify the one existing, by following the same logic used to add/rm IP address on a DN.

6.2 Useful tools

6.2.1 Proxy Comparison

Item	Apache2 (Debian/Ubuntu)	httpd (RHEL/AlmaLinux)	HAProxy (all systems)
Main config file	/etc/apache2/apache2.conf	/etc/httpd/conf/httpd.conf	/etc/haproxy/haproxy.cfg
VHost config directories	/etc/apache2/sites-available/ a2ensite / a2dissite → sites-enabled/	/etc/httpd/conf.d/	Defined as frontend/backend in haproxy.cfg
VHost activation	/etc/ssl/certs/, /etc/ssl/private/	Auto-loaded via conf.d/*.conf	No activation; everything is in haproxy.cfg
SSL certificate locations	In each VirtualHost with SSLCertificateFile	/etc/pki/tls/certs/, /etc/pki/tls/private/	/etc/haproxy/certs/ or /etc/ssl/private/
SSL declaration	/var/www/html/ or VirtualHost DocumentRoot	Same in <VirtualHost *:443>	bind with ssl crt /path/file.pem
HTML pages location	/var/www/html/ or VirtualHost DocumentRoot	/var/www/html/ or VirtualHost	Not applicable (HAProxy doesn't serve HTML)
Log files	/var/log/apache2/	/var/log/httpd/	/var/log/haproxy.log (via rsyslog)
systemd service	apache2.service	httpd.service	haproxy.service
Service control cmds	systemctl start/stop/reload apache2	systemctl start/stop/reload httpd	systemctl start/stop/reload haproxy

Table 2: Apache2, httpd, and HAProxy Comparison

6.2.2 Create a ACME account

In order to use the `acme.sh` script, you will probably need to create a `acme` account, related to an email, on which you will be updated on the deadline of the certificate issuance.

It can be done thanks to a command such as :

```
acme.sh --register-account --accountemail email@example.com --server letsencrypt
```

For further documentation, see this page : https://www.ans.co.uk/docs/domains/ssl/letsencrypt/letsencrypt_acme_sh

6.3 Documentation

6.3.1 Main links

- Official repo `acme.sh` <https://gitlab.cern.ch/jeedy/load-balancer/letsencrypt>
- More about `acme.sh` :
 - Cheatsheet : <https://peterbabic.dev/blog/cheatsheet-acme-sh-dns/>
 - General informations : https://www.ans.co.uk/docs/domains/ssl/letsencrypt/letsencrypt_acme_sh/
 - French Official Documentation : <https://cyber.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/document/anssi-fondamentaux-securisation-acme-v1.0.pdf>
 - Prerequisites to use ACME with custom API : <https://aao.fyi/bits/systems/acmesh-setup/>
- About DNS-01 Challenge :
 - <https://wiki.archlinux.org/title/Acme.sh>
 - https://www.certwarden.com/docs/user_interface/providers/dns01_acme.sh/
- Construct a DNS API : <https://github.com/acmesh-official/acme.sh/wiki/DNS-API-Dev-Guide>
- On Proxy :
 - <http://www.haproxy.org/download/1.4/doc/configuration.txt>
 - <https://www.haproxy.com/documentation/haproxy-configuration-tutorials/proxying-essentials/configuration-basics/backends/>

6.3.2 Debug Ressources

- CNAME and ACME : <https://blog.narf.ssji.net/2024/09/30/renew-dns-01-lets-encrypt/>
- DNS alias mode : <https://community.letsencrypt.org/t/acme-sh-support-domain-alias-mode/52700>
- Proxy auto-reload with ACME : <https://www.haproxy.com/blog/haproxy-and-let-s-encrypt/>
- Default certificate when SNI disabled :
 - <https://serverfault.com/questions/510132/apache-sni-namevhosts-always-route-to>
 - <https://beamtic.com/apache-default-vhost-problem>

6.3.3 Other links

- Wildcard certificates : <https://www.eff.org/deeplinks/2018/02/technical-deep-dive-security>
- On Apache :
 - Reverse proxy Apache guide : https://httpd.apache.org/docs/2.4/howto/reverse_proxy.html
 - Apache usecase : <https://www.digitalocean.com/community/tutorials/how-to-use-apache-proxy-extension-ubuntu-20-04>
 - Apache server setup : <https://www.digitalocean.com/community/tutorials/how-to-install-the-apache-web-server-on-ubuntu-20-04>
AND
<https://www.linode.com/docs/guides/install-and-use-apache-on-almalinux/>
 - Apache reverse proxy as a SNI : [https://www.xolphin.com/support/Apache/Apache_-_Server_Name_Indication_\(SNI\)](https://www.xolphin.com/support/Apache/Apache_-_Server_Name_Indication_(SNI))

